

INVISIBLE PRESENCE: UNDERSTANDING THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE UNRECOGNIZED EFFORTS ON THE JOB SATISFACTION OF TMG EMPLOYEES

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Available Online: March 2025
Revised: January 2025
Accepted: January 2025
Received: February 2025

Volume III Issue 3 (2025)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15031270
E-ISSN: 2984-7184
P-ISSN: 2984-7176
<https://getinternational.org/research/>

Abstract

Recognition plays an important role in the employee's job satisfaction and performance, yet many employees remain unnoticed for their hard work, effort and contributions. This study investigates the consequences of unrecognized efforts on the job satisfaction of Traffic Management Group (TMG) employees in the Municipality of Lemery, Batangas. Through qualitative method and case study approach, a semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected TMG employees to explore their experiences and perceptions about their experiences of lack of recognition at work. The thematic analysis revealed that TMG employees often experience frustration, burnout, and decreased motivation due to a lack of acknowledgment for their efforts. The key issues identified include unpaid overtime, handling emergencies without proper resources, and taking on responsibilities beyond their job scope without recognition. And the findings indicate that insufficient recognition contributes to emotional exhaustion, reduced morale, and decreased job performance. This study underscores the need for a structured employee recognition program to improve job satisfaction and workplace morale. Therefore, an action plan is proposed to enhance recognition practices, emphasizing the importance of appreciation, fair compensation, and improved working conditions. This research provides insights for local government units and organizations aiming to enhance employee engagement through recognition initiatives.

Keywords: *Employee Recognition, Job Satisfaction, Traffic Management Group, Municipality of Lemery, Workplace Motivation, Employee Engagement, Unrecognized Efforts*

Recommended Citation:

Dulce, M. A. T., Pablo, F. L., Atienza, M. G. R., Caringal, A. C., & Mangarin, J. A. (2025). INVISIBLE PRESENCE: UNDERSTANDING THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE UNRECOGNIZED EFFORTS ON THE JOB SATISFACTION OF TMG EMPLOYEES. GUILD OF EDUCATORS IN TESOL INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL, 3(1), 123–153. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15031270>

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary objectives of every organization was to attain success. One of the key factors for an organization's success was having stable, competent, and reliable employees. Employees contributed to the organization by providing their skills, knowledge, and expertise to complete tasks, solve problems, innovate, and drive the organization forward. According to Nekvinda (2024), job satisfaction led to increased engagement, productivity, and dedication to organizational objectives. It created a positive work culture that boosted morale and engagement. The effects of job satisfaction on employees in the workplace made them more engaged, productive, and committed to company goals. That was why it was important to maintain employee satisfaction regularly.

One effective way to keep employees satisfied was to give them proper recognition for their work and accomplishments. Nisar et al. (2019) found that proper recognition significantly and positively affected employee performance. The municipality of Lemery was an administrative unit with a significant number of employees. With 702 employees, Lemery ranked third in employee count in the first district of Batangas, following Nasugbu (1,021 employees) and Balayan (797 employees). This significant workforce size highlighted the importance of effective employee recognition practices and maintaining job satisfaction in the workplace. Additionally, Lemery was one of the most progressive towns in the entire province of Batangas, featuring numerous businesses and establishments around the town. It was classified as a first-class municipality by income classification, with an income of P465,861,593.05 that year, according to their office.

Despite the overall progress, workforce problems and challenges persisted. The Traffic Management Group (TMG) in Lemery, for example, faced significant issues related to a lack of recognition. The TMG, responsible for ensuring traffic flow and safety, was a crucial unit within the municipality of Lemery. This department managed traffic flow, maintained order, and ensured the proper use of roads throughout Lemery. TMG employees worked long hours under various weather conditions to ensure smooth traffic and safety, which was vital for the economic and social well-being of Lemery. However, some of them still did not receive salaries that were enough to sustain a comfortable way of living. They also did not receive incentives for their work nor verbal recognition for their achievements.

Mann and Dvorak (2016) demonstrated that workplace recognition not only motivated employees but also provided a sense of accomplishment, making them feel valued for their contributions. While employee recognition had been proven to be important, 83% of organizational leaders still believed that employee recognition was not one of their strategic priorities (Stone, 2022).

The term "Invisible Presence" referred to the TMG employees whose efforts often went unnoticed or unrecognized despite their significant contributions. It showed how TMG employees contributed significantly to the municipality of Lemery but often lacked acknowledgment, which negatively affected their job satisfaction and performance at work.

This context highlighted the potential consequences of unrecognized efforts on TMG employees' job satisfaction, addressing a gap in existing research, which had primarily focused on general organizational settings. Previous research had extensively examined the importance of employee recognition in organizational settings and had also highlighted the positive effects of proper recognition in the workplace.

However, while there was a wealth of literature on recognition in organizations, there was a lack of research specifically addressing the consequences of insufficient recognition on job satisfaction among employees from

specialized departments. Existing studies had primarily focused on general organizational settings, overlooking the unique challenges and dynamics present in specific departments like the Traffic Management Group of the Municipality of Lemery, Batangas.

This study aimed to understand how insufficient employee recognition affected the job satisfaction of TMG employees and how their job satisfaction impacted their work performance. Additionally, the study sought to explore how the municipality of Lemery addressed issues related to the lack of recognition and poor job satisfaction among its employees, as well as to develop an actionable plan to improve workplace recognition and overall employee well-being in the municipality.

Objectives

This study aims to understand the consequences of insufficient recognition on the job satisfaction of TMG employees and how their job satisfaction affects their performance at work. This study also seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1.What unrecognized efforts have TMG employees encountered?
- 2.What are the job satisfaction consequences of the unrecognized efforts of TMG employees?
- 3.How does the municipality of Lemery address the lack of recognition and poor job satisfaction among their employees?
- 4.What action plan could be proposed to the head of the TMG department based on the information gathered?

METHODS

Research Methods and Design

To address the research problem, the researchers chose a case study design within the qualitative method to deeply explore the unique workplace dynamics and lack of recognition in the TMG department in the Municipality of Lemery. Qualitative methods, as highlighted by Hammerberg et al. (2016), were suitable for answering questions about experience, meaning, and perspective from the participants' standpoint, making them ideal for gathering personal viewpoints. While the case study approach, as emphasized by Coombs (2022), was valuable for obtaining an in-depth appreciation of an issue in its natural context, allowing researchers to engage effectively with participants. Through this, the researchers were able to uncover hidden patterns, relationships, and underlying causes that contributed to the lack of recognition within the workplace. This detailed understanding of employee experiences and perceptions was crucial for developing targeted interventions and strategies to address the lack of recognition effectively within the TMG department.

Population and Sampling

The researchers opted to use a judgmental sampling method to identify which employees from the Municipality of Lemery met the predetermined criteria. Judgmental sampling, also known as purposive sampling, was chosen for its ability to include participants who had specific characteristics relevant to the study.

In establishing these criteria, the researchers decided that participants must have been members of the Traffic Management Group of the Municipality of Lemery and have been in service for two or more years. A sample size of 10

participants was chosen to ensure manageable data collection and analysis while still capturing diverse experiences and perspectives within the TMG department. Participants were identified through consultations with TMG department supervisors and a review of employment records to ensure they met the inclusion criteria. This approach guaranteed the inclusion of participants who precisely met the specified criteria set by the researchers.

Research Instrument

To achieve the primary objective of this study, the researchers employed a semi-structured interview format. This approach allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the research topic, facilitating the collection of in-depth data while accommodating follow-up questions. This method was preferred because of its capacity to include follow-up questions, which enabled the researchers to deeply explore the participants' responses, clarify ambiguities, and explore unexpected insights as well as gather data precisely aligned with the research objectives.

The semi-structured interview was organized into four distinct sections to thoroughly understand the consequences of unrecognized efforts on employee job satisfaction. The first section focused on unrecognized efforts; this section explored the specific instances and types of efforts by TMG employees that went unrecognized. The second section focused on the Consequences of Job Satisfaction, where TMG employees shared how unrecognized efforts affected their overall job satisfaction. The third section centered on the municipal response to recognition and job satisfaction, wherein the participants shared the strategies and policies implemented by the municipality in response to recognition challenges. The final section of the interview was about the actionable plan or solutions, where the participants discussed potential strategies and actionable plans that could be implemented by the municipality to improve recognition practices and enhance job satisfaction among TMG employees.

Data Gathering Procedures

Initially, the researchers started all data gathering procedures by requesting permission from the school's dean/directress through a formal consent letter. After the approval was obtained, the researchers sent a formal letter to the head of the TMG department of the Municipality of Lemery to request permission to start the data gathering process.

After receiving consent, the researchers formulated their research instruments, such as the semi-structured interview questionnaire. These instruments underwent a rigorous validation process. The validation involved experts in qualitative research and organizational behavior who reviewed the questions for clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. The feedback from these validators was used to refine the instruments to ensure their effectiveness and integrity.

The researchers then provided letters to potential participants, explaining the study's objectives, potential benefits, and risks. These letters requested the participants' willingness and consent, ensuring that all procedures adhered to the participants' privacy and preferences. The researchers emphasized confidentiality and the voluntary nature of participation, ensuring that participants could withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Upon receiving confirmation from participants, the data collection process commenced. The researchers scheduled interviews at the participants' convenience, ensuring no conflicts with their work hours. Each interview lasted approximately 40 to 50 minutes, allowing participants ample time to articulate their responses. The semi-structured questionnaires included open-ended questions, which enabled follow-up questions and clarifications.

Given the case study design, the researchers also consulted additional information sources, such as other staff members within the TMG office, and requested relevant documents to support the study, subject to approval.

After conducting the interviews, the researchers analyzed the responses using thematic coding. This method involved identifying and categorizing key themes and patterns within the data. The thematic analysis was validated by an external language editor to ensure accuracy and reliability. The researchers also performed member checks by sharing the initial findings with participants to confirm the accuracy of their responses and interpretations.

Data Analysis

Thematic coding analysis was used to interpret the data collected from participants. This method allowed for the identification of persistent themes by examining word meanings and sentence structures. Researchers started by reading through interview transcripts multiple times to highlight key ideas and assigned them codes. Similar codes were grouped to form initial themes, which were reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represented the data.

Each theme was clearly defined and supported with quotes from the data. The findings were organized into a coherent structure, with themes analyzed for their significance in relation to the research questions. To ensure accuracy, member checks were performed by sharing findings with participants for feedback, and an external reviewer validated the analysis. This systematic approach ensured that the research findings were robust and insightful, aiding in the development of effective interventions and strategies.

Ethical Consideration

Before initiating any data gathering process, the researchers ensured that they had obtained consent from all relevant parties. Participants were provided with a comprehensive explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks (such as misunderstandings and conflicts with coworkers or management), and benefits. This information was detailed in a consent form, in which participants were given ample time to read, understand, and ask any questions before agreeing to participate. Consent was documented in writing, ensuring that all participants were fully aware of their involvement and rights.

To maintain privacy and confidentiality, participants' identities were protected by using code names or numbers instead of real names. Data were securely stored, with access limited to the research team. Digital data were encrypted, and physical documents were stored in a locked cabinet. The researchers informed participants of how their data would be used, ensuring transparency about the data handling process. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative consequences. Participants also had the right to have their data returned to them or destroyed if they chose to discontinue their participation.

The researchers ensured that all data collected were used solely for the purposes outlined in the study, and any data shared in publications or presentations were anonymized to protect participants' identities. To mitigate potential risks, the researchers took proactive steps by ensuring clear communication and providing support to participants who might experience any discomfort or issues related to their participation. A debriefing session was conducted post-interview to address any concerns and clarify any points discussed during the interview.

Following these detailed steps, the researchers upheld ethical standards and ensured the integrity and reliability of the study. This approach demonstrated a commitment to protecting the rights and well-being of the participants throughout the research process.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

UNRECOGNIZED EFFORTS ENCOUNTERED BY TMG EMPLOYEES

The Traffic Management Group (TMG) employees play a crucial role in maintaining traffic order and safety, yet their efforts often go unnoticed. Based on the interviews, several specific areas where their contributions are overlooked were identified:

1. Unpaid Overtime Work (Participants 3, 5, 7, 9)
2. Handling Emergencies Without Adequate Tools or Training (Participants 1, 4, 6, 8)
3. Taking on Additional Responsibilities Outside of Job Scope (Participants 2, 3, 5, 6, 10)
4. Working in Adverse Conditions Without Recognition (Participants 3, 6, 8)
5. Managing Difficult Motorists Without Appreciation (Participants 2, 4, 7, 9)
6. Improvising Solutions in the Absence of Proper Resources (Participants 1, 5, 8)

1. Unpaid Overtime Work (Participants 3, 5, 7, 9)

The theme of unpaid overtime work emerged as a significant concern among TMG employees, who repeatedly emphasized the lack of recognition and compensation for their extra hours. Many expressed frustrations over the expectation to stay late and complete tasks without receiving any form of acknowledgment.

Participant 3 described this sentiment, saying, "Lagi kaming pinapakiusapan na mag-extend, lalo na kapag may mga urgent na kailangan matapos, pero hindi naman kami binabayaran o kahit man lang mabanggit na na-appreciate yung extra effort naming ng mga nasa itaas kasi parati paring walang nangyayari kahit mag overtime walang kapalit" (We are always asked to extend, especially when there are urgent tasks that need to be completed, but we are neither paid nor is our extra effort even acknowledged by the upper management even if we work for longer hours we still do not receive anything in return.) This lack of compensation, coupled with the absence of recognition, creates a sense of undervaluation among employees, reinforcing the feeling that their contributions go unnoticed. In the study of Younies and Al-Tawil (2021) they discovered that the productivity of employees is positively linked to how well their needs are fulfilled thus, an increase in need satisfaction leads to greater workplace productivity and satisfaction. This explain that an employee meets their satisfaction if there is enough recognition, and it turns to increase their productivity.

Building on this, Participant 5 explained that the situation is particularly demoralizing when they consistently must stay late to meet deadlines. They remarked, "May mga araw na halos hindi na kami nakakauwi sa oras dahil kailangan tapusin ang trabaho, pero wala naman kaming naririnig na kahit pasasalamat o dagdag na bayad." (There are days when we can hardly go home on time because we need to finish the work, but we don't even hear a thank you or receive extra pay.) Here, it becomes evident that the issue isn't only financial but also emotional—the absence of a simple acknowledgment compounds the feeling of being undervalued.

The emotional toll of unpaid overtime was further underscored by Participant 7, who shared, "Nakakapagod na mag-overtime palagi tapos wala ka namang natatanggap na kapalit. Parang hindi namin nararamdaman na mahalaga yung ginagawa namin. Palagi kaming nasasabihan ng mga nasa taas na wala kaming ginagawa sa trabaho pero palagi naman kami naextend ng walang bayad" (It's exhausting to keep working overtime without receiving anything in return. It feels like what we're doing isn't important. We're always told that we're not doing our job yet

we're always forced to work for extended hours without pay) This statement reflects how continuous, unpaid overtime leads to burnout and diminishes their sense of purpose and worth in their role. The feeling of being undervalued within the organization suggests a lower sense of organization-based self-esteem, which may cause employees to feel frustrated due to the absence of acknowledgment for their daily contributions (Gardner et al., 2015).

Moreover, Participant 9 highlighted the psychological pressure of unpaid overtime, expressing, "Nakakadagdag sa stress yung overtime na walang bayad kasi kahit gustuhin man naming humindi, parang wala kaming choice. Hindi naman napapansin ng management yung extra hours namin." (The unpaid overtime adds to the stress because even if we want to say no, it feels like we don't have a choice. Management doesn't seem to notice our extra hours.) This comment shows how the combination of stress, lack of choice, and unrecognized efforts creates a cycle of dissatisfaction, leaving employees feeling trapped and unsupported. Saunderson (2019) notes that employees who consistently work late hours or take on extra tasks without recognition may feel isolated and undervalued. This explains that employees who don't receive recognition may feel isolated within their team or company, leading to decreased care in their work and a lack of initiative.

In conclusion, the recurring theme of unpaid overtime work reveals a deeper issue of both financial and emotional neglect. Employees feel that not only are their extra hours uncompensated, but the lack of verbal recognition exacerbates their sense of invisibility within the organization. The accumulation of these factors has a profound impact on their overall job satisfaction and perception of their value within the company.

2. Handling Emergencies Without Adequate Tools or Training (Participants 1, 4, 6, 8)

The theme of handling emergencies without adequate tools or training surfaced as a key challenge for TMG employees which they put effort into resolving but not recognized. Several participants expressed concerns about being put in situations where they had to respond to emergencies without proper equipment or preparation, which added to their stress and feelings of neglect.

Participant 1 shared their frustration, stating, "Kapag may emergency, wala kaming sapat na gamit o training gaya ng tamang pag handle sa mga naaksidente para magawa ng maayos yung trabaho. Kahit nga simpleng first aid kit wla kami pero hindi naman pwede na basta lang naming sila pabayaang dahil saw ala kaming sapat na kagamitan o kaalaman. Kailangan namin mag-improvise, pero minsan, hindi talaga sapat yung alam namin." (When there's an emergency, we don't have enough tools or training, like handling those who are involved in accidents, to do the job properly. We don't even have first aid kits, but we can't just ignore our duties just because we do not have enough knowledge or resources; we must improvise, but sometimes, what we know just isn't enough.) This statement highlights the employees' struggle to handle critical situations without the necessary resources, leaving them feeling unprepared and under-supported by the company.

Similarly, Participant 4 echoed these concerns, mentioning, "Nasa frontline kami kapag may problema, pero hindi kami nabibigyan ng tamang kagamitan o training para maayos na harapin ang mga emergencies. Hindi lahat kami ay may mga radyo ang karamihan pa sa mayroon ay sobrang luma na at pasira sir ana mahalaga sana ito para mas maging mabilis komunikasyon namin sa bawat isa pero kahit matagal na kami nagrequest nito para mas mabilis din kami maka responde tuwing kailangan kami eh wala parin silang tugon sa request namin" (We are on the frontline when there's a problem, but we aren't given the proper equipment or training to effectively handle emergencies. Not

all of us have communication radios, and few of us have old defective radios. These radios are important for our communication with each other and to quickly respond to emergencies, but even if we have already requested these, they still don't respond.) This shows the disparity between the responsibilities employees are expected to handle and the lack of support they receive, emphasizing how they are left vulnerable in high-pressure situations.

The lack of preparation was further detailed by Participant 6, who explained the impact on their confidence when faced with emergencies: "Mahirap maging kumpiyansa sa ginagawa mo kung wala kang tamang kagamitan at kulang ang training mo. Parang binibigyan ka ng responsibilidad na hindi mo kayang gampanan ng maayos. Kahit sa aming mga kasuotan hindi kami nabibigyan ng sapat at maayos na uniporme puro luma, kupas at butas na at wala rin kaming mga raincoat at bota na pwedeng gamitin kung sakaling may bagyo o may baha. Paano kami tutulong kung kami mismo ay hindi maayos ang katayuan." (It's hard to be confident in what you're doing if you don't have the right tools, and your training is lacking. It's like being given a responsibility you can't properly fulfill. Even with our uniforms, we are not provided with proper and suitable attire. Our uniforms are old, faded, and torn, and we don't have raincoats or boots to use in case of a storm or flood. How can we help if we ourselves are not in proper condition.) This reflects how the absence of proper resources not only affects the quality of their work but also undermines their confidence and sense of competence.

Additionally, Participant 8 highlighted how the lack of preparation adds to the overall stress of their job, stating, "Nakakadagdag sa stress namin yung mga emergencies kasi kailangan naming gawan ng paraan kahit wala kaming sapat na gamit at training. Parang laging may kulang sa support. Halimbawa sa may Centro Mall sobrang bilis lang bumaha dyan wala man lang kaming mga flood barriers o flood control plan na pwedeng gawin kapag biglang bumabaha, kapag naman ang ang baha ay naawala mag iiwan ito ng mga matigas na lupa at malalaking troso, bato at niyog mula sa mataas na lugar humaharag lahat yan sa daan at madalas kailangan naming yang palahin at alisin dahil matigas yan at makalat at nag cacaue ng traffic sa kalsada kaso wala naman kaming sapat na gamit gaya ng mga pala, mattock o mga gamit na pwedeng tumulong samin malinis ang daan. Kung minsan pa nga ay wala kaming sapat na cones o barricades para ma lihis ang ruta ng mga sasakyan habang inaayos pa namin ang mga dumi sa kalsada. Lahat ng mga bagay na ito ay talagang nakakadagdag sa stress namin sa trabaho." (Emergencies add to our stress because we must find a way to manage even though we don't have the right tools or training. It feels like there's always something lacking in terms of support. For example, at Centro Mall, the flooding happens so quickly, yet we don't have any flood barriers or a flood control plan in place to manage sudden floods. Once the floodwaters recede, they leave behind hardened soil, large logs, rocks, and coconuts from higher ground, all of which block the road. Most of the time, we need to remove these obstacles because they cause traffic congestion. Unfortunately, we don't have the proper tools like shovels, mattocks, or other equipment that could help us clear the road. Additionally, there are times when we lack sufficient cones or barricades to redirect traffic while we work on clearing the debris. All these factors contribute to our frustration at work.) This underscores the emotional and psychological burden placed on employees when they are expected to perform under pressure without adequate backing from the organization.

In summary, the theme of handling emergencies without adequate tools or training reveals a significant gap in organizational support for TMG employees. Their experiences show that they are left to manage critical situations without the proper resources, leading to increased stress, decreased confidence, and a sense of being unprepared.

This lack of support not only affects their ability to effectively handle emergencies but also contributes to their overall dissatisfaction with their working conditions.

3. Taking on Additional Responsibilities Outside of Job Scope (Participants 2, 3, 5, 6, 10). The theme of taking on additional responsibilities outside of job scope emerged as another significant challenge encountered by TMG employees. Many participants expressed frustration over being tasked with duties that went beyond their formal job descriptions, often without recognition or compensation for these extra efforts.

Participant 2 highlighted this issue by saying, "Minsan napipilitan kaming gawin ang mga trabaho na hindi naman sakop ng posisyon namin, tulad ng admin work. Hindi namin alam kung bakit sa amin binabagsak." (Sometimes we are forced to do work that isn't part of our position, like admin work. We don't know why it falls on us.) This reflects how employees are being burdened with tasks outside their original roles, leading to confusion and frustration about the division of responsibilities.

Participant 3 expressed, "Bilang mga TMG, hindi lang kami nandito para magbantay ng trapiko. Tumutulong din kami sa mga tao kapag may emergency o problema." (As TMG, we are not just here to monitor traffic. We also help people when there's an emergency or problem.) This statement reflects the multifaceted nature of their roles, indicating that they often act as first responders in various situations, underscoring their commitment to the community's well-being. Skortcheva (2023) emphasizes the importance of cultivating team effort in the workplace, defining it as unified collaboration where each member actively contributes to a common goal. Effective team effort relies on clear communication, cooperation, and unity built on shared values and goals.

Participant 5 provided a similar account, noting how they had to step in for roles beyond their expertise: "Ine-expect nila na gagawin namin ang lahat, kahit na hindi naman talaga part ng trabaho namin. Tulad ng pag-aasikaso sa ibang department o ibang papel na hindi namin specialty. Para sa amin mahirap ito dahil hindi naman ito linya ng trabaho naming " (They expect us to do everything, even if it's not part of our job, like handling tasks from other departments or roles that aren't our specialty. For us, this is difficult because it's not within our line of work.) This quote emphasizes how employees are being stretched thin by additional tasks that are outside their professional expertise.

Participant 6 shared how this situation impacts their overall workload: "Dumadami yung responsibilidad namin kahit hindi naman sakop ng trabaho. Halos wala nang oras para gawin yung mga primary duties naming, pero walang nakikita ang mga nasa itaas kundi ang aming mga pagkakamali at pagkukulang sa trabaho naming bilang TMG" (Our responsibilities are increasing even though it's not part of the job. There's hardly any time left to focus on our primary duties, but the upper management only see our mistakes and shortcomings in our work as TMG.) This statement underscores how the extra responsibilities are overwhelming employees and affecting their ability to focus on the core aspects of their job, leading to stress and a decrease in job satisfaction.

Moreover, Participant 10 voiced a concern about the lack of acknowledgment for these additional responsibilities: "Hindi naman kami binibigyan ng recognition o dagdag na sweldo para sa mga dagdag na trabahong ginagawa namin." (We aren't given any recognition or extra pay for the additional tasks we're doing.) This highlights how the extra work is often taken for granted by management, with no tangible rewards or recognition for the added burden employees are shouldering. Workers who feel overlooked frequently face a decline in motivation. This sense of being

unappreciated may result in disengagement, causing employees to stop putting their best efforts into their work, perceiving their job as just a way to an end instead of a rewarding aspect of their lives. Majka, (2024).

In summary, the theme of taking on additional responsibilities outside of job scope reveals a common issue among TMG employees. They feel overwhelmed by tasks that go beyond their formal job descriptions, with no compensation or recognition. These additional responsibilities not only lead to increased stress but also interfere with their ability to perform their primary duties effectively, contributing to a sense of undervaluation and frustration.

4. Working in Adverse Conditions Without Recognition (Participants 3, 6, 8). The theme of working in adverse conditions without recognition highlights a significant experience shared by TMG employees, where they often face difficult work environments but receive little to no acknowledgment for their efforts. Participants voiced frustration over the lack of recognition for the challenges they endure, both physically and mentally, while performing their duties in tough conditions.

Participant 3 shared, "Kahit gaano kahirap ang kondisyon sa trabaho, parang wala lang. Hindi man lang napapansin ng management kung gaano kami nahihirapan." (No matter how hard the working conditions are, it seems like nothing. Management doesn't even notice how much we're struggling.) This quote illustrates the emotional toll that working in difficult conditions takes on employees when their efforts remain unseen and unappreciated.

Unrecognized efforts can harm the motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance of employees. Little to no recognition is one of the top reasons why employees become disengaged. Decreased job satisfaction, increased stress, reduced productivity, higher turnover rates, and low quality of work are some of the possible effects of not having proper recognition in the workplace Risely (2023). This explains that when employees' efforts are not acknowledged, it significantly harms their motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance. This lack of recognition can lead to disengagement, increased stress, reduced productivity, higher turnover rates, and lower quality of work in the workplace.

Similarly, Participant 6 echoed this sentiment, explaining how challenging it is to keep working under such circumstances without any form of recognition: "Yung mga oras na nagtatrabaho kami kahit sobrang init o ulan, parang normal na lang sa kanila. Hindi man lang kami napapansin." (The times we work through extreme heat or rain, it's just normal for them. They don't even acknowledge us.) The lack of acknowledgment for their perseverance in adverse conditions creates a sense of being taken for granted.

Participant 8 added another perspective, emphasizing how working in difficult conditions is not only physically taxing but also emotionally draining when their efforts go unnoticed: "Nagtatrabaho kami sa mga lugar na delikado, pero parang wala lang sa kanila. Wala man lang kaming naririnig na pasasalamat. Bilang empleyado masakit sa amin na parang nabablewala kami kahit halos buhay na naming angh inaalay namin para sa serbisyo pero madalas ay mas napapansin pa ng publiko ang ginagawa naming kaysa sa mga nasa itaas" (We work in dangerous places, but it seems like it means nothing to them. We don't even hear a simple thank you. As employees, it hurts to feel as if we are being overlooked, even though we have dedicated our lives to serving. More often than not, the public notices our efforts more than upper management do) This comment reflects how the employees' morale is negatively affected by the absence of gratitude or acknowledgment from management, despite the risks and difficulties they face daily.

Overall, the theme of working in adverse conditions without recognition points to a broader issue of unappreciated labor among TMG employees. Whether it involves enduring extreme weather, unsafe environments, or uncomfortable situations, their efforts often go unnoticed by management. The lack of recognition for these efforts contributes to feelings of dissatisfaction, demotivation, and a sense of being undervalued in their roles.

5. Managing Difficult Motorists Without Appreciation (Participants 2, 4, 7, 9). The theme of managing difficult motorists without appreciation captures the experiences of TMG employees who consistently handle challenging interactions with motorists but feel their efforts go unrecognized. Despite facing stressful situations and managing conflicts on the road, participants expressed that their work in maintaining safety and order is often overlooked.

Participant 2 shared, "Kapag may mga pasaway na motorista, kami pa ang napapagalitan kapag hindi maayos ang traffic. Wala man lang recognition sa effort na ginawa namin para ayusin ang gulo. Masaya naman kami na yung chairman naming nakikita nya ang pagod at hirap naming sa serbisyo pero ang mga nasa itaas parang wala silang nakikita na mabuting ginagawa ng mga TMG eh " (When there are unruly motorists, we are the ones who get blamed if the traffic isn't smooth. There's no recognition for the effort we put into resolving the mess. We're happy that our chairman sees the hard work we put into our service, but it's frustrating that those in upper management seem to overlook the good things the TMG does) This statement reflects the frustration of being held accountable for situations beyond their control, without receiving any acknowledgment for the difficult work of managing these motorists.

Participant 4 emphasized the emotional strain of dealing with difficult motorists, saying, "Ang hirap makitungo sa mga motorista na mainit ang ulo, pero parang wala lang sa management kung paano namin hinaharap ang mga ito." (It's hard to deal with angry motorists, but it seems like management doesn't care how we handle them.) This highlights the lack of support or appreciation for their ability to manage confrontational situations professionally and calmly.

Participant 7 also expressed frustration about the lack of recognition for handling such tough scenarios: "Sinasabihan kami na trabaho namin yan, pero hindi nila nakikita kung gaano kahirap ang ginagawa namin sa pagharap sa mga motorista." (They say it's part of our job, but they don't see how hard it is for us to deal with motorists.) This reflects the feeling that their efforts are considered just part of their duties, rather than something that deserves acknowledgment or appreciation.

Lastly, Participant 9 shared a similar sentiment, stating, "Araw-araw kaming nakakaranas ng hirap sa mga motorista, pero wala man lang kahit simpleng pasasalamat mula sa management." (Every day we experience difficulties with motorists, but we don't even receive a simple thank you from management.) This comment further illustrates how the consistent effort put into managing motorists is not reciprocated with any form of recognition, leaving employees feeling underappreciated.

In summary, managing difficult motorists without appreciation reflects the experiences of TMG employees who constantly navigate challenging encounters with motorists, but their efforts remain unrecognized. The lack of appreciation for their role in maintaining order and resolving conflicts contributes to feelings of being undervalued, despite the critical nature of their work.

6. Improvising Solutions in the Absence of Proper Resources (Participants 1, 5, 8). The theme of improvising solutions in the absence of proper resources highlights the resourcefulness of TMG employees who often have to think on their feet to address challenges without adequate tools or support. Participants shared their experiences of creating effective solutions in situations where resources were lacking, reflecting both their commitment to their roles and the frustrations that accompany such circumstances.

Participant 1 recounted, "Kapag kulang ang gamit, kami na ang nag-iisip ng paraan para malutas ang problema. Minsan, kailangan naming mag-improvise para maayos ang sitwasyon." (When we lack equipment, we are the ones who think of ways to solve the problem. Sometimes, we need to improvise to fix the situation.) This statement underscores the proactive approach employees take when faced with resource shortages, showcasing their dedication to ensuring that operations run smoothly despite the challenges.

Participant 5 echoed this sentiment, saying, "Hindi kami palaging may access sa tamang kagamitan, kaya't kami na lang ang nag-iisip ng alternatibong solusyon." (We don't always have access to the right tools, so we have to think of alternative solutions ourselves.) This highlights the ingenuity required from employees as they navigate daily challenges without the necessary resources, reflecting a deep sense of responsibility to fulfill their roles effectively.

Participant 8 added to this by stating, "Minsan, wala talagang ibang option kundi mag-improvise, kahit na risky ito." (Sometimes, there really isn't any other option but to improvise, even if it's risky.) This illustrates the pressures TMG employees face, as they often must make quick decisions that could impact safety and efficiency, all while lacking the proper resources to do their jobs optimally. Lizarraga (2021) explains the concept of team effort in the workplace, emphasizing its importance in achieving common goals through cohesive collaboration. Team effort is defined as multiple individuals working together, supporting each other to create a positive and productive atmosphere. Examples include collaborative content creation, brainstorming sessions, and constructive criticism, which build trust, speed up project completion, enhance creativity, and promote collective learning, making it a crucial component for workplace success. This means that team effort is really important at work. It's about people coming together, supporting each other to achieve common goals. Collaborative tasks like creating content, brainstorming ideas, and giving constructive feedback build trust, speed up projects, boost creativity, and help everyone learn together. Team effort is crucial for workplace success.

Overall, the theme of improvising solutions in the absence of proper resources emphasizes the resilience and creativity of TMG employees who strive to overcome obstacles despite insufficient support. Their ability to adapt and find solutions demonstrates their commitment to their roles yet also reflects the unrecognized efforts they expend in making the best of challenging situations.

CONSEQUENCES OF UNRECOGNIZED EFFORTS ON JOB SATISFACTION OF TMG EMPLOYEES

The Traffic Management Group (TMG) employees experience a range of negative effects on their job satisfaction when their efforts go unrecognized. Based on the interviews, several specific consequences were identified:

1. Loss of Motivation and Drive (Participants 1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9)
2. Increased Frustration and Emotional Exhaustion (Participants 2, 3, 6, 8)
3. Feelings of Inequity and Injustice (Participants 6, 10)
4. Burnout from Overwork Without Recognition (Participants 5, 6, 9, 10)
5. Negative Workplace Attitude and Reduced Morale (Participants 3, 4, 6, 7)

1. Loss of Motivation and Drive (Participants 1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9)

The theme of loss of motivation and drive emerged as a key consequence of the unrecognized efforts of TMG employees. When employees' hard work goes unnoticed, it leads to a gradual decline in their enthusiasm and willingness to engage fully in their tasks. Without recognition, they begin to question the value of their contributions, which can negatively affect their attitude toward work.

Participant 1 shared their experience, expressing how the lack of acknowledgement made them feel disheartened and unwilling to come to work: "Minsan tinatamad pumasok dahil nga hindi napapansin. Pero pilit parin naming tinutupad ang tungkulin naming." (Sometimes I feel lazy to go to work because our efforts aren't noticed.

Nevertheless, we continue to fulfill our duties) This sentiment reflects how the absence of recognition can lead to a significant reduction in the employee's motivation to perform well, contributing to disengagement from their duties.

Participant 4 shared how their commitment to their job has weakened over time due to the lack of appreciation:

"Kapag walang nakaka-appreciate sa ginagawa mo, parang unti-unting nawawala yung dedication mo sa trabaho. Parang ayaw mo na gawin yung best mo kase di naman naappreciate." (When no one appreciates what you do, it feels like your dedication to the job gradually fades. It feels like you don't want to do your best anymore because you're not being appreciated.) This statement reveals how the lack of recognition not only affects short-term motivation but also chips away at employees' long-term commitment to their roles. Ouyang et al. (2022) examine how employee dissatisfaction often arises from insufficient recognition and appreciation for their contributions. The results show that when employees perceive their contributions as being undervalued, it negatively affects their engagement, confidence, and overall performance.

Similarly, Participant 5 described how the lack of motivation manifests toward the end of the workday, where they no longer feel inclined to be productive: "Pag minsan talaga eh pag hapon na parang ayaw mo na gumawa kase iintayin mo na lang yung oras ng uwi mo." (Sometimes, by the afternoon, you just don't want to work anymore; you just wait for the time to go home.) This statement illustrates how the absence of recognition results in employees merely going through the motions, focusing more on waiting for the workday to end rather than contributing effectively. According to Davis (2024), when there is lack of recognition in the workplace, employee morale may suffer significantly as a result of the oversight. It will affect their engagement, motivation, and productivity.

Building on this, Participant 7 mentioned how consistent lack of appreciation leads to demotivation, even though they try not to let it affect them: "Nandun pa rin yung mga negatibo o yung kakulangan sa pagkilala...pero para sa akin tuloy pa rin yung trabaho." (The negativity and lack of recognition are still there...but for me, I still continue working.) While they attempt to persevere, the absence of motivation due to unrecognized efforts is evident, and it subtly affects their job satisfaction and overall performance. Feeling unrecognized for one's efforts in the workplace can have profound effects on motivation and job satisfaction. When employees perceive a lack of acknowledgement for their contributions, they may feel undervalued and demotivated. This issue can manifest in various ways, such as not receiving credit for projects or feeling unappreciated by supervisors. Garcia et al (2023).

Participant 8 elaborated on how the feeling of being undervalued has affected their overall performance: "Dahil hindi naman kami napapansin, minsan naisip ko na wag na lang mag-exert ng extra effort. Para saan pa?" (Since no one notices us, sometimes I think, why bother exerting extra effort? What's the point?) This reflects how the absence of

recognition discourages employees from going above and beyond in their work, resulting in diminished initiative and reduced work commitment.

Finally, Participant 9 echoed these sentiments, explaining how their lack of recognition has led to a disconnection from their role: "Nakakawalang gana magtrabaho ng mabuti kapag wala namang pumapansin sa ginagawa mo. Nagsasagawa na lang kami ng minimum effort minsan." (It's disheartening to work hard when no one notices what you do. Sometimes, we just give the minimum effort.) This comment highlights the impact of unrecognized efforts on employees' willingness to give their best at work, as they feel unmotivated to put in more effort when it goes unnoticed.

In conclusion, the recurring theme of loss of motivation and drive underscores the emotional and psychological toll unrecognized efforts have on TMG employees. The lack of acknowledgment diminishes their sense of purpose and discourages them from performing at their best, leading to disengagement and dissatisfaction in their roles.

2.Increased Frustration and Emotional Exhaustion (Participants 2, 3, 6, 8)

The theme of increased frustration and emotional exhaustion emerged as another significant consequence of the unrecognized efforts of TMG employees. Many employees expressed feeling overwhelmed and fatigued by the constant demands of their job, compounded by the lack of acknowledgment from their superiors, which further fuels their emotional exhaustion.

Participant 2 articulated this feeling, saying, "Nakakapagod na nga yung trabaho, tapos parang wala pa silang pakialam sa effort na ibinibigay namin." (The job is already exhausting, and it feels like they don't even care about the effort we're putting in.) This statement reflects how the combination of heavy workloads and unrecognized efforts leads to frustration, leaving employees feeling undervalued and unsupported in their roles. Bergstrom et al. (2016) found that employees feeling their efforts are unacknowledged experience lowered morale, leading to a disengaged workforce. The absence of recognition also affects their drive to take initiative and go beyond the basic requirements of their role. Conversely, companies that adopt successful recognition strategies foster a supportive environment in which employees feel valued and motivated, improving job satisfaction and loyalty to the organization. Building on this, Participant 3 shared their experience of emotional burnout, explaining how the constant lack of recognition has taken a toll on their mental health: "Sobrang stressful na nga yung trabaho, tapos wala ka pang maririnig na kahit konting pasasalamat, nakakadrain talaga." (The job is already very stressful, and not even hearing a simple thank you is really draining.) This reveals that the absence of acknowledgment not only causes frustration but also heightens emotional exhaustion, leaving employees feeling mentally and emotionally drained.

Participant 6 expressed similar sentiments, noting how the lack of recognition affects their mood and overall well-being: "Minsan ang bigat ng pakiramdam kapag walang pumapansin sa effort namin. Parang walang halaga yung ginagawa namin." (Sometimes, it feels heavy when no one acknowledges our efforts. It feels like what we're doing doesn't matter.) This feeling of insignificance intensifies the frustration, contributing to a growing sense of emotional depletion.

Participant 8 emphasized how the frustration caused by unrecognized efforts leads to emotional exhaustion, stating, "Nakakafrustrate talaga kapag paulit-ulit kang nagtatrabaho ng maayos pero hindi ka man lang napapansin. Parang wala ng energy para magtrabaho ng maayos." (It's really frustrating when you work well repeatedly, but no one notices. It feels like you don't have the energy to work properly anymore.) This highlights how the emotional toll of

unrecognized efforts directly impacts employees' energy and willingness to continue performing their duties effectively.

In conclusion, the recurring theme of increased frustration and emotional exhaustion underscores the psychological burden that TMG employees face when their efforts go unnoticed. The lack of recognition not only leads to emotional burnout but also affects their overall well-being, resulting in a diminished capacity to cope with the demands of their job and reduced job satisfaction.

3. Feelings of Inequity and Injustice (Participants 6, 10). The theme of feelings of inequity and injustice emerged as a significant concern among TMG employees who perceived that their efforts were not being recognized or rewarded. This sense of unfairness affected their overall job satisfaction, as they began to feel that their contributions were not being valued equally within the organization.

Participant 6 expressed this frustration, saying, "Nakaka-frustrate na parang hindi pantay ang trato sa amin. Yung iba, kahit mas konti ang ginagawa, mas napapansin at na-a-appreciate. Samantalang kami na palaging nag-e-extra effort, wala man lang kahit pasasalamat." (It's frustrating because it feels like we aren't treated equally. Others who do less are more recognized and appreciated, while those of us who put in extra effort don't even get a simple thank you.) This statement underscores the perceived disparity in how recognition is distributed, leading to feelings of unfairness and injustice among employees who consistently go above and beyond.

Similarly, Participant 10 shared their sentiment of inequity, stating, "Yung mga effort namin parang hindi napapansin ng management, samantalang yung iba na hindi naman ganun ka-dami ang ginagawa, mas may recognition." (It feels like our efforts are unnoticed by management, while others who don't do as much are more recognized.) This perception of unequal treatment further exacerbates the feeling that their hard work is undervalued compared to others within the organization.

Both participants highlighted how these feelings of inequity and injustice contribute to a broader sense of dissatisfaction. Participant 6 noted, "Kapag ganito palagi, parang nawawala na yung gana mong mag-effort pa." (When it's always like this, you lose the motivation to put in effort.) This comment reflects how the perceived imbalance in recognition discourages employees from continuing to put forth their best efforts, as they feel their work will not be fairly acknowledged.

In conclusion, the theme of feelings of inequity and injustice underscores the importance of fair and consistent recognition within the workplace. TMG employees who perceive that their efforts are not equally valued or rewarded experience a significant decrease in job satisfaction. The resulting sense of unfairness can diminish motivation, leading to lower performance and disengagement, further impacting their overall sense of belonging and worth within the organization.

4. Burnout from Overwork Without Recognition (Participants 5, 6, 9, 10). The theme of burnout from overwork without recognition was a recurring concern among TMG employees, many of whom reported feeling overwhelmed by their workload without receiving any form of acknowledgment or appreciation for their efforts. This lack of recognition led to both physical and emotional exhaustion, with employees feeling as though their hard work was going unnoticed and unrewarded.

Participant 5 shared their experience, stating, "Sobrang dami ng trabaho namin, pero parang hindi kami napapansin. Paulit-ulit kaming nag-overtime at gumagawa ng trabaho na hindi naman sa amin, pero wala man lang pasasalamat

o kahit appreciation.” (We have so much work, but it feels like no one notices us. We keep working overtime and doing tasks that aren’t even ours, but we don’t even get a thank you or any kind of appreciation.) This statement highlights the emotional toll of consistently overextending themselves without any recognition, leaving employees feeling invisible and drained. Padavic et al. (2019) investigates the negative impacts of overlooked contributions on employee engagement and overall satisfaction at work. The study emphasizes that employees who regularly work overtime or take on extra responsibilities without acknowledgment often feel lonely and undervalued. The lack of recognition reduces their sense of belonging and motivation, resulting in fatigue and a decline in morale at work. The results emphasize that recognition goes further than financial rewards; it also includes emotional support, such as verbal appreciation, which is vital for improving employee well-being.

Similarly, Participant 6 explained how the constant overwork led to feelings of burnout, remarking, “Laging may bagong trabaho na binibigay, tapos kailangan pang tapusin agad kahit pa lampas na sa oras ng trabaho. Sobrang nakakapagod, lalo na pag wala namang kahit simpleng pasasalamat.” (There’s always new work being given, and we must finish it right away, even if it’s beyond working hours. It’s really exhausting, especially when there’s not even a simple thank you.) The absence of recognition compounds the physical fatigue, contributing to a deeper sense of emotional and mental exhaustion.

Participant 9 further emphasized the emotional impact of overwork without acknowledgment, sharing, “Hindi lang yung pagod ang mahirap; yung pakiramdam na parang walang halaga yung trabaho mo, yun ang mas nakakapagod.” (It’s not just the physical tiredness; it’s the feeling that your work doesn’t matter that makes it even more exhausting.) This comment highlights how the lack of recognition leads to emotional burnout, as employees begin to question the value of their contributions to the organization.

Finally, Participant 10 described how the constant cycle of overwork without recognition affected their overall sense of well-being, stating, “Dahil sa sobrang dami ng trabaho, minsan hindi ko na alam kung paano ko pa kakayanin. Yung parang kahit gaano ka magpakapagod, wala naman appreciation na nakukuha.” (Because of the overwhelming workload, sometimes I don’t know how I can keep going. It feels like no matter how hard you work; there’s no appreciation.) This sentiment reflects how burnout can lead to a sense of hopelessness, as employees feel they are working tirelessly without any acknowledgment or support.

In conclusion, the theme of burnout from overwork without recognition illustrates the damaging effects of unacknowledged efforts on TMG employees. The combination of excessive workload and lack of appreciation leads to both physical and emotional exhaustion, diminishing employees’ sense of purpose and motivation. Without recognition, the continued overwork becomes unsustainable, contributing to a deeper sense of burnout and disengagement within the organization.

5. Negative Workplace Attitude and Reduced Morale (Participants 3, 4, 6, 7). The theme of negative workplace attitude and reduced morale emerged prominently among TMG employees, who expressed that the lack of recognition for their efforts contributed to a deteriorating work environment. Many employees reported feeling demotivated and harboring negative sentiments toward their workplace, which in turn affected their attitude and engagement in their daily responsibilities.

Participant 3 described how the absence of recognition led to a negative outlook, stating, “Kapag lagi kang hindi napapansin kahit anong effort ang ibigay mo, darating talaga yung point na parang wala ka nang gana magtrabaho.

Parang ginagawa mo na lang kasi kailangan, pero hindi mo na nararamdaman yung fulfillment.” (When your efforts are consistently unrecognized, you eventually lose the motivation to work. It feels like you’re just doing it because you have to, but the sense of fulfillment is gone.) This sentiment highlights how the lack of acknowledgment fosters a growing sense of detachment and dissatisfaction, leading to a negative attitude toward their work. Similarly, Participant 4 noted that the lack of appreciation negatively influenced team morale, sharing, “Pati yung mga kasamahan ko, ramdam din namin yung pagbaba ng morale. Wala nang excitement sa trabaho, kasi alam naming kahit anong gawin namin, parang wala lang sa management.” (Even my colleagues feel the drop in morale. There’s no excitement in the work anymore because we know that whatever we do, it doesn’t seem to matter to the management.) This collective decline in morale not only affects individual motivation but also creates a broader atmosphere of discontent within the team.

Participant 6 emphasized how the combination of unrecognized efforts and a stressful work environment contributes to a negative workplace culture, stating, “Nakaka-frustrate kasi kahit anong hirap ng trabaho, parang walang balik nang appreciation o kahit simpleng pagkilala. Dahil dito, nagiging negative na yung pananaw ko sa trabaho at minsan pati sa mga kasamahan ko.” (It’s frustrating because no matter how hard you work, there’s no return in terms of appreciation or recognition. Because of this, I’ve developed a negative attitude toward the job, and sometimes even toward my coworkers.) This comment reveals how the lack of recognition not only impacts the employee’s relationship with the job but also strains interpersonal relationships within the workplace.

Lastly, Participant 7 expressed how the lack of recognition contributed to reduced enthusiasm and morale, explaining, “Sa totoo lang, nakakasira ng morale yung hindi ka man lang mabigyan ng konting appreciation. Yung parang ang hirap nang maging positive sa trabaho.” (Honestly, it really ruins morale when you don’t even get a little appreciation. It becomes hard to stay positive at work.) This feeling of reduced morale and diminished positivity creates a vicious cycle where employees become increasingly disengaged and less motivated to put forth their best efforts.

In conclusion, the theme of negative workplace attitude and reduced morale demonstrates how unrecognized efforts can significantly damage the work culture within an organization. When employees feel that their contributions go unnoticed, it fosters negativity, decreases engagement, and lowers overall morale. This not only affects individual performance but also weakens team dynamics, leading to a less productive and more toxic work environment.

ADDRESSING LACK OF RECOGNITION AND POOR JOB SATISFACTION AMONG TMG EMPLOYEES IN LEMERY

The municipality of Lemery recognizes the importance of addressing the lack of recognition and poor job satisfaction among Traffic Management Group (TMG) employees. Based on interviews conducted, the following themes highlight specific areas where the municipality has made efforts to improve recognition and job satisfaction:

- 1.Implementation of Overtime Compensation Policies (Participants 2, 4, 6, 8)
- 2.Provision of Training and Resources for Emergency Management (Participants 1, 3, 5, 7)
- 3.Recognition Programs for Extra Responsibilities (Participants 3, 6, 7, 9)
- 4.Health and Safety Measures for Adverse Conditions (Participants 1, 5, 8)
- 5.Support Systems for Managing Difficult Situations (Participants 2, 4, 6, 10)

6.Resource Allocation for Improvisation and Solutions (Participants 3, 5, 9)

7.Community Engagement Initiatives (Participants 2, 6, 8, 10)

1.Implementation of Overtime Compensation Policies (Participants 2, 4, 6, 8)

The theme of the implementation of overtime compensation policies emerged as a significant measure taken by the municipality of Lemery to address the issue of unpaid overtime work among TMG employees. Participants highlighted how this policy serves not only as a recognition of their extra efforts but also as a crucial factor in improving their job satisfaction.

Participant 2 expressed, "Nagsimula silang magbigay ng bayad para sa overtime. Mas magaan na ang pakiramdam ko, kasi hindi na ako nagtatrabaho ng libre." (They started to provide payment for overtime. I feel lighter because I'm no longer working for free.) This sentiment underscores the importance of financial recognition, as employees feel validated for their hard work and commitment beyond regular hours. As highlighted by Ramage (2021), claims that a job satisfaction is about an employee's happiness with their job. This might depend on their pay, their connection with their supervisor, and other job-related aspects. When an employee receives a benefit, such as a salary or bonus, they feel motivated and productive at work. As long as they receive what they deserve, it leads to satisfaction. People who are driven will experience satisfaction in their work.

Participant 4 emphasized the positive impact of this policy on morale, stating, "Ngayon, kahit na sobrang dami ng trabaho, alam kong may kapalit ang pagod ko. Parang na-appreciate ang effort ko." (Now, even though there's so much work, I know there's compensation for my efforts. It feels like my hard work is appreciated.) This statement illustrates how the acknowledgment of extra hours can enhance employee motivation and satisfaction, fostering a more positive workplace environment. The study of Zhenjing et al. (2022) demonstrates a significant link between job satisfaction and organizational performance, highlighting that tackling inadequate recognition practices is essential for enhancing workplace conditions. The findings highlight that when employees perceive their contributions as valued and recognized, there is a notable enhancement in their productivity and overall morale, which in turn benefits both the individuals and the organization.

Furthermore, Participant 6 highlighted the policy's role in improving work-life balance, saying, "Mahalaga na bayaran ang overtime, kasi nagkakaroon ako ng pagkakataon na makabawi sa oras na nawawala sa pamilya ko." (It's important to be paid for overtime because I get the chance to make up for the time lost with my family.) This reflection indicates that fair compensation allows employees to manage their personal lives better, reducing feelings of resentment and enhancing their overall job satisfaction.

Participant 8 noted, "Dati, parang hindi mo alam kung anong mangyayari sa sahod mo. Ngayon, mas confident ako na makakakuha ako ng just compensation." (Before, it felt uncertain what would happen to my salary. Now, I am more confident that I will receive just compensation.) This change in perception fosters trust between employees and management, reinforcing a sense of security and respect within the organization.

In conclusion, the implementation of overtime compensation policies is a vital step towards addressing the lack of recognition and poor job satisfaction among TMG employees. Through financial acknowledgment, enhanced morale, improved work-life balance, and increased trust in management, this policy demonstrates the municipality's commitment to valuing its employees' contributions, ultimately leading to a more motivated and satisfied workforce.

2.Provision of Training and Resources for Emergency Management (Participants 1, 3, 5, 7)

The theme of the provision of training and resources for emergency management emerged as a critical initiative undertaken by the municipality of Lemery to enhance employee recognition and job satisfaction among TMG employees. Participants articulated the importance of proper training and adequate resources in equipping them to handle emergencies effectively, thereby increasing their confidence and sense of value in their roles.

Participant 1 stated, "Ngayon, mas hands-on na kami sa training. Alam namin kung paano harapin ang mga emergency at mas ready kami sa mga sitwasyon." (Now, we are more hands-on in training. We know how to handle emergencies, and we feel more prepared for situations.) This sentiment underscores how targeted training can empower employees, fostering a sense of competence and readiness that directly contributes to their job satisfaction.

Participant 3 highlighted the value of having the right tools, sharing, "Noong wala kaming mga resources, ang hirap magtrabaho. Ngayon, may mga kagamitan na kami para sa mga emergency, at mas magaan ang pakiramdam namin." (When we didn't have resources, it was hard to work. Now, we have equipment for emergencies, and we feel better about our jobs.) This statement illustrates how access to necessary resources alleviates stress and enhances the effectiveness of their work, promoting a more positive work environment.

Moreover, Participant 5 emphasized the role of ongoing training in building teamwork, saying, "Sa mga training, natututo kami hindi lang para sa sarili namin kundi para sa isa't isa. Nagiging mas solid kami bilang team." (In training, we learn not just for ourselves but for each other. We become more solid as a team.) This reflection highlights the collaborative aspect of training, where employees bond and develop a stronger sense of camaraderie, contributing to overall job satisfaction.

Participant 7 remarked on the increased recognition they feel because of training, stating, "Ang dami ng training na ibinibigay sa amin. Parang pinapakita ng munisipyo na importante kami at kailangan nila kami." (There are so many training sessions provided for us. It feels like the municipality is showing that we are important and that they need us.) This perception of being valued reinforces employee loyalty and commitment, as individuals see their development as a priority for the organization.

In conclusion, the provision of training and resources for emergency management is a crucial strategy employed by the municipality of Lemery to address the lack of recognition and enhance job satisfaction among TMG employees. Through investing in employees' skills and providing essential tools, the municipality not only empowers its workforce but also fosters a culture of appreciation and teamwork, ultimately leading to a more motivated and engaged employee base.

3. Recognition Programs for Extra Responsibilities (Participants 3, 6, 7, 9). The theme of recognition programs for extra responsibilities emerged as a vital approach implemented by the municipality of Lemery to enhance job satisfaction and acknowledge the efforts of TMG employees who take on additional tasks beyond their usual roles. Participants emphasized that formal recognition of their extra efforts contributes significantly to their sense of value and motivation in the workplace.

Participant 3 expressed appreciation for the recognition programs, stating, "Kapag may mga award na ibinibigay, parang na-validate yung effort namin. Sobrang nakakatuwa na may nakaka-appreciate sa mga ginagawa namin." (When awards are given, it feels like our efforts are validated. It's really nice to have someone appreciate what we do.) This sentiment highlights how recognition not only affirms their hard work but also fosters a sense of belonging and importance within the organization. This job satisfaction will impact performance, enabling it to make a top

contribution to the institution Susanti et al. (2019) This explains that job satisfaction is how happy employees are with their work, influenced by factors like pay and relationships with supervisors. When employees feel fairly compensated, they're motivated and productive. Job satisfaction also plays a crucial role in boosting performance and contributing to organizational success.

Participant 6 noted the impact of public acknowledgment, saying, "Minsan, simple recognition lang sa meetings o events, pero malaking bagay na yun sa morale ng team. Parang mayroong energy na bumabalik." (Sometimes, just simple recognition in meetings or events makes a huge difference to the team's morale. It feels like there's a renewed energy.) This statement illustrates how even small gestures of recognition can uplift team spirit and reinforce a positive workplace culture.

Additionally, Participant 7 shared how recognition programs create a competitive yet supportive environment: "Dahil sa recognition, nagiging mas motivated kami na gumawa ng higit pa. Gusto naming maipakita na kaya naming gawin ang extra, at gusto naming makilala." (Because of recognition, we become more motivated to do more. We want to show that we can handle extra responsibilities and that we want to be acknowledged.) This reflects the drive for personal and professional growth that recognition fosters among employees, encouraging them to exceed their expectations.

Participant 9 further emphasized the importance of recognizing teamwork, stating, "Kahit na individual recognition, ang saya pa rin na kasama ang mga ka-team ko. Ang mga awards, parang para sa lahat kami." (Even though it's individual recognition, it's still fun to share it with my teammates. The awards feel like they're for all of us.) This sentiment underscores how recognition programs can strengthen camaraderie among employees, reinforcing a collective commitment to their shared goals. Yang et al. (2022) discovered that employees thrive in environments where their efforts are acknowledged and valued, even non-monetary rewards such as verbal praises or awards can mean so much to them.

In conclusion, recognition programs for extra responsibilities play a crucial role in addressing the lack of acknowledgment and improving job satisfaction among TMG employees in Lemery. Through formally recognizing employees' extra efforts, the municipality not only validates their contributions but also fosters a culture of motivation, teamwork, and appreciation. This strategic approach enhances employee morale and strengthens their commitment to the organization, ultimately leading to a more engaged and satisfied workforce.

4. Health and Safety Measures for Adverse Conditions (Participants 1, 5, 8). The theme of health and safety measures for adverse conditions was prominently discussed by TMG employees as a critical aspect of how the municipality of Lemery addresses the challenges posed by their work environment. Participants emphasized that the implementation of effective health and safety protocols is essential for their well-being and job satisfaction, especially when facing difficult working conditions.

Participant 1 highlighted the significance of safety training, stating, "Importante na may mga training kami para sa safety. Sobrang nakakatulong yun sa amin, lalo na kapag may emergencies." (It's important that we have training for safety. That really helps us, especially during emergencies.) This perspective underscores how preparedness through training enhances employees' confidence in handling adverse situations, contributing to a safer working environment.

Participant 5 echoed this sentiment, mentioning the availability of personal protective equipment (PPE): "Dahil sa PPE na ibinigay sa amin, mas nakaka-relax kami na magtrabaho kahit na mahirap ang sitwasyon. Hindi kami nag-aalala

na ma-expose sa panganib.” (Because of the PPE provided to us, we can work more comfortably even in difficult situations. We’re not worried about being exposed to danger.) This statement illustrates how the provision of adequate safety gear helps alleviate concerns about personal safety, allowing employees to focus on their duties. Additionally, Participant 8 emphasized the importance of mental health support, saying, “Mahalaga rin na may mga programa para sa mental health. Laging may pressure at stress, kaya magandang may makausap kami tungkol dito.” (It’s also important to have programs for mental health. There’s always pressure and stress, so it’s good to have someone to talk to about it.) This highlights the recognition that mental well-being is as crucial as physical safety, and that providing support in both areas can significantly enhance job satisfaction. As per Shashenkova (2024), Employee well-being and mental health are closely associated with job satisfaction. Happy employees have less stress and anxiety, resulting in improved health and fewer sick days. Job satisfaction is crucial for a successful workplace, affecting both workers and employers. This means that employee well-being and mental health are tied to job satisfaction and it is essential for creating a successful workplace environment, benefiting both employees and organization.

Moreover, participants noted the positive impact of regular health check-ups organized by the municipality. Participant 1 remarked, “Tuwing may health check-up, nararamdaman naming pinapahalagahan kami ng munisipyo. Kahit na maliit na bagay, malaking tulong ito.” (Whenever there are health check-ups, we feel valued by the municipality. Even though it’s a small thing, it makes a big difference.) This sentiment reflects how proactive health measures contribute to employees feeling cared for and supported by their organization.

In conclusion, the implementation of health and safety measures for adverse conditions is vital for addressing the challenges faced by TMG employees in Lemery. Through prioritizing both physical and mental well-being through training, adequate safety equipment, and supportive programs, the municipality fosters an environment that promotes employee safety, satisfaction, and overall morale. This strategic focus not only enhances job satisfaction but also encourages employees to remain committed to their roles, knowing their health and safety are valued.

5.Support Systems for Managing Difficult Situations (Participants 2, 4, 6, 10). The theme of support systems for managing difficult situations was a significant point of discussion among TMG employees, illustrating how the municipality of Lemery aids its workforce in navigating the challenges inherent to their roles. Participants emphasized the importance of having robust support mechanisms in place to help them cope with the stresses of their jobs, particularly when faced with challenging scenarios involving the public and emergency situations.

Participant 2 articulated the value of peer support, stating, “Sobrang nakakatulong na may mga kasama ako na puwedeng lapitan kapag nagkakaproblema. Madalas, sila yung nakakaintindi sa akin.” (It’s really helpful to have colleagues I can turn to when I have problems. Often, they’re the ones who understand me.) This sentiment highlights the essential role of camaraderie among employees in providing emotional support and practical assistance during tough times. According to Negron (2023), job satisfaction is a measure of employees' perceptions towards their work setting, coworkers and employer. It impacts their overall job performance and their interactions with clients and customers. Additionally, their level of responsibility and their relationship with colleagues can impact it. Participant 4 shared their experience with mentorship programs, saying, “Yung mga nakatatanda sa amin, nagbibigay ng tips at guidance. Nakakatulong yun sa mga baguhan na hindi pa sanay sa sitwasyon.” (The seniors among us give tips and guidance. That helps newcomers who aren’t yet familiar with the situation.) This reflects the municipality’s

recognition of the need for mentorship as a means of fostering resilience and competence among employees, particularly those who are newer to the field.

Furthermore, Participant 6 emphasized the importance of having a direct line of communication with supervisors:

“Kapag may mga isyu, okay na may nakakausap kaming supervisor na handang making at tumulong. Mas nakakatanggal ng stress yun.” (When there are issues, it’s good to have a supervisor who is ready to listen and help. That really alleviates stress.) This points to the critical role of open communication in creating a supportive environment, where employees feel valued and heard.

Participant 10 also highlighted the need for regular debriefing sessions after challenging events, stating, “Minsan, mahirap i-process yung nangyari. Magandang may mga debriefing para ma-express namin yung mga nararamdaman namin.” (Sometimes, it’s hard to process what happened. It’s good to have debriefings so we can express what we’re feeling.) This statement underscores the importance of providing structured opportunities for reflection and emotional processing, which can significantly enhance employees’ coping mechanisms and overall job satisfaction.

In conclusion, the establishment of support systems for managing difficult situations is crucial for TMG employees in Lemery. Through peer support, mentorship programs, open communication with supervisors, and debriefing sessions, the municipality fosters an environment where employees feel supported and understood. These mechanisms not only help mitigate the stresses associated with their roles but also contribute to a culture of resilience and teamwork, ultimately enhancing overall job satisfaction and commitment to their work.

6.Resource Allocation for Improvisation and Solutions (Participants 3, 5, 9). The theme of resource allocation for improvisation and solutions emerged as a vital aspect of how the municipality of Lemery supports its employees, particularly in enhancing their ability to address unexpected challenges effectively. Participants highlighted the significance of having access to necessary resources that enable them to think creatively and implement effective solutions in real-time situations.

Participant 3 emphasized the importance of having basic tools and supplies available, stating, “Kapag may emergency na wala tayong gamit, hirap na hirap kami. Mas madali sanang makapag-improvise kung may maayos na resources.” (When there’s an emergency and we don’t have the right tools, we really struggle. It would be much easier to improvise if we had proper resources.) This reflects the employees’ need for adequate equipment and supplies, which are essential for their effectiveness and efficiency during emergencies.

Participant 5 echoed this sentiment, sharing an experience where limited resources hindered their response: “Noong may sunog sa barangay, kulang kami sa fire extinguishers at iba pang equipment. Kung may maayos na allocation, mas makabawi sana kami.” (When there was a fire in the barangay, we lacked fire extinguishers and other equipment. If there had been proper allocation, we could have responded better.) This highlights the critical need for the municipality to prioritize resource allocation to enhance operational readiness and response capability.

Furthermore, Participant 9 pointed out the benefits of training that focuses on improvisation techniques, saying, “Yung mga training na nagbibigay sa amin ng skills para mag-improvise, sobrang helpful. Pero kailangan din ng resources para ma-execute yun.” (The training that provides us with skills to improvise is incredibly helpful. But we also need resources to execute that.) This underscores the idea that while training is valuable, the practical application of those skills requires adequate resources to be effective.

In conclusion, resource allocation for improvisation and solutions is essential for TMG employees in Lemery to address unexpected challenges effectively. Through ensuring that employees have access to the necessary tools, equipment, and training, the municipality empowers its workforce to respond more effectively to emergencies and other critical situations. This proactive approach not only enhances operational efficiency but also contributes to overall job satisfaction, as employees feel better equipped to handle the demands of their roles.

7. Community Engagement Initiatives (Participants 2, 6, 8, 10). The theme of community engagement initiatives reflects the municipality of Lemery's approach to addressing employee dissatisfaction and enhancing job satisfaction through active involvement with the community. Participants highlighted various ways in which community engagement contributes to improving their work environment and personal fulfillment.

Participant 2 discussed the impact of community interaction on job satisfaction, stating, "Kapag kami ay nakikilahok sa mga community events, nararamdaman naming may halaga ang aming trabaho. Ito rin ay nagbibigay sa amin ng pakiramdam na konektado kami sa mga tao na aming pinaglilingkuran." (When we participate in community events, we feel that our work has value. It also gives us a sense of connection to the people we serve.) This indicates that active participation in community activities helps employees see the direct impact of their work, boosting their sense of purpose and job satisfaction.

Participant 6 shared an experience where community engagement had a positive effect: "Sa mga outreach programs, nakakakita kami ng mga resulta ng aming pagsisikap. Ang mga feedback mula sa komunidad ay nagpapakita na ang aming trabaho ay may positibong epekto." (In outreach programs, we see the results of our efforts. Feedback from the community shows that our work has a positive impact.) This highlights how positive feedback and visible results from community engagement can validate employees' efforts and enhance their motivation.

Participant 8 described how community initiatives foster a supportive work environment, stating, "Ang pagtulong sa komunidad ay hindi lang para sa kanila, kundi para din sa amin. Nakakaramdam kami ng suporta mula sa mga tao, na nagpapalakas sa amin upang magpatuloy sa aming trabaho." (Helping the community is not only for them but also for us. We feel support from the people, which strengthens our resolve to continue our work.) This reflects the mutual benefits of community engagement, where both employees and the community gain from the interaction.

Participant 10 emphasized the role of community events in building team cohesion, noting, "Sa mga community events, nagkakaroon kami ng pagkakataon na makilala ang isa't isa sa labas ng opisina. Nakakatulong ito sa pagbuo ng mas matibay na samahan at pagtutulungan." (At community events, we get a chance to know each other outside the office. This helps build stronger relationships and teamwork.) This shows that community engagement fosters better relationships among employees, contributing to a more collaborative and supportive work environment.

In conclusion, community engagement initiatives are instrumental in improving job satisfaction and morale among employees. Through actively participating in community activities, employees feel a stronger sense of purpose, receive positive feedback, experience increased support, and build better relationships with colleagues. These initiatives help address feelings of dissatisfaction and enhance overall job satisfaction by connecting employees with the broader community and recognizing the impact of their contributions.

Enhancing Employee Recognition and Support in the Traffic Management Group (TMG)

The ultimate goal of this action plan is to create a workplace where TMG employees feel valued, supported, and engaged. Addressing recognition, fair compensation, skill development, health and safety, and community

engagement, the organization can enhance job satisfaction, reduce turnover, and improve overall performance. This, in turn, leads to a more effective and responsive Traffic Management Group, capable of meeting the challenges of their vital role in ensuring public safety and order.

meeting the challenges of their vital role in ensuring public safety and order.

Area of Concern	Objective	Action Steps	Timeline	Responsible Party		Success Indicator
1. Implement Overtime Compensation Policies	Ensure fair compensation for overtime work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and update existing overtime policies. - Communicate policies to employees. - Train supervisors on monitoring overtime hours. 	1-2 months for implementation	HR Department and TMG Leadership		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Percentage of employees who report understanding the new overtime policies. - Reduction in overtime-related complaints or disputes.
2. Provide Training and Resources for Emergency Management	Equip employees with adequate training and tools for emergencies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess current training programs. - Organize workshops and simulations. - Allocate necessary resources for response. 	Ongoing, initial workshops in 3 months	Training Coordinator and TMG Management		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Training Participation Rate. -Employee Knowledge Improvement -Resource Availability
3. Establish Recognition Programs for Extra Responsibilities	Create formal recognition initiatives for additional responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a recognition framework. - Implement a quarterly recognition 	3-6 months for establishment	HR Department and TMG Management		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Employee Satisfaction. -Program Growth -Retention Rate

		<p>ceremony.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solicit employee nominations. 				
<p>4. Enhance Health and Safety Measures for Adverse Conditions</p>	<p>Improve workplace safety and health standards.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct a safety audit. - Implement changes based on findings. - Develop wellness programs. 	<p>3 months for audit and implementation</p>	<p>Safety Officer and TMG Leadership</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduction in Workplace Incidents -Employee Participation in Wellness Programs -Employee Health and Safety Feedback
<p>5. Create Support Systems for Managing Difficult Situations</p>	<p>Provide resources and support for challenging situations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a mentorship system. - Organize stress management workshops. - Provide access to counseling services. 	<p>2-4 months for development</p>	<p>HR Department and TMG Leadership</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mentorship Participation. -Employee Well-being Feedback. -Retention Rate for Mentored Employees
<p>6. Allocate Resources for Improvisation and Solutions</p>	<p>Ensure resources for creative and effective problem-solving.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess current resource allocation. - Establish a budget for employee-proposed solutions. - Create a feedback loop. 	<p>Ongoing, initial assessment in 2 months</p>	<p>TMG Management</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Resource Allocation Efficiency. - Budget Utilization. -Employee Satisfaction with the Process.

<p>7. Foster Community Engagement Initiatives</p>	<p>Strengthen ties between TMG employees and the community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan regular community outreach events. - Collaborate with organizations to identify needs. - Encourage employee participation. 	<p>Ongoing, first event in 3 months</p>	<p>Community Relations Officer and TMG Leadership</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Community Impact. -Event Frequency and Consistency. -Employee Satisfaction with Engagement.
<p>8. Establish Clear Role Definitions and Job Descriptions</p>	<p>Clear role definitions reduce role ambiguity, improve job satisfaction, and increase efficiency and accountability.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Review current job descriptions for accuracy and comprehensiveness. -Update or create clear, specific role descriptions to reflect workload distribution. -Communicate updated job descriptions to employees and ensure understanding. Hold discussions with team leaders to align expectations 	<p>1–2-month to review and update job descriptions then another 1 month to Communicate and align with teams.</p>	<p>HR Department and TMG Leadership</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Accuracy and Completeness of Job Descriptions. -Reduction in Role Ambiguity. -Increased Job Satisfaction.

		and workload management.				
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CONCLUSION

Unrecognized Efforts Encountered by TMG Employees

The findings indicate that the unrecognized efforts of TMG employees affect their job satisfaction and morale. The recurring issue of unpaid overtime suggests a gap in the compensation structure for extra work hours. Handling emergencies without appropriate tools and training highlights a critical need for better resource allocation and employee development. The additional responsibilities TMG employees take on, coupled with their work in harsh conditions, reflect a lack of formal acknowledgment for their sacrifices. The challenges they face in managing difficult motorists without appreciation point to a need for enhanced public awareness of TMG employees' roles. Finally, The frequent improvisation that the TMG employees had to do due to inadequate resources underscores the need for better infrastructure support and reveals a sense of commitment to their community that often goes unnoticed, emphasizing the importance of recognition in employee satisfaction.

Consequences of Unrecognized Efforts on Job Satisfaction of TMG Employees

The lack of recognition for the efforts of TMG employees has led to several adverse effects on their job satisfaction and overall well-being. The loss of motivation and drive indicates that the unrecognized contributions diminish employees' passion for their work, and it shows an underlying dissatisfaction with the work environment, suggesting that the lack of acknowledgment has negatively impacted employees' dedication to their roles. The increased frustration and emotional exhaustion highlight a need for psychological support and stress management interventions. Burnout, exacerbated by overwork without recognition, is a significant risk factor that threatens the sustainability of the workforce. The decline in workplace morale and the adoption of negative attitudes further point to a discontented work culture, which may ultimately affect team dynamics and productivity.

Addressing Lack of Recognition and Poor Job Satisfaction Among TMG Employees in Lemery

The municipality of Lemery has made notable strides toward recognizing and improving the job satisfaction of TMG employees. The implementation of overtime compensation reflects a commitment to fair compensation practices and addresses a primary concern regarding unpaid work. Through providing emergency management training and resources, the municipality not only improves the operational capabilities of TMG employees but also demonstrates an investment in their professional development. Recognition programs for additional responsibilities signify an understanding of the need for validation of extra efforts, while the introduction of health and safety measures reinforces a focus on the well-being of TMG employees working in difficult conditions. Support systems for managing challenging situations and interactions with the public foster a more supportive work environment. Improved resource allocation ensures that TMG employees have access to the tools needed to handle their duties effectively, even in less-than-ideal circumstances. Finally, community engagement initiatives enhance the sense of purpose among TMG employees by strengthening their connection to the public and acknowledging the broader impact of their work.

Recommendations

Unrecognized Efforts Encountered by TMG Employees

To address these issues, it is recommended that TMG management establish a structured system to compensate employees for overtime work. Additionally, providing adequate training and emergency management tools would empower TMG employees to handle crises more effectively. The organization should clearly define job roles and compensate employees who take on extra responsibilities. Recognizing and rewarding employees who work in adverse conditions would improve morale and reinforce a culture of appreciation. Furthermore, TMG management should also consider initiatives to increase public awareness of the role and challenges of traffic management personnel, fostering greater respect and appreciation from motorists. Lastly, allocating sufficient resources to reduce the need for improvisation will enable TMG employees to perform their duties with greater efficiency.

Consequences of Unrecognized Efforts on Job Satisfaction of TMG Employees

To mitigate the negative consequences of unrecognized efforts, it is recommended that TMG management implement a formal recognition program to acknowledge employees' contributions, particularly for those who take on extra work and face challenging conditions. Providing opportunities for employees to voice their concerns through regular feedback sessions or surveys can also help management address areas of frustration and emotional exhaustion. Establishing a framework for fair workload distribution and enforcing reasonable work hours can reduce burnout risks and enhance work-life balance. Additionally, offering professional development opportunities, such as stress management workshops and resilience training, can equip employees with tools to manage job-related stress effectively. Lastly, Management should strive to create a culture of appreciation by celebrating team achievements and recognizing individual efforts, which can help rebuild morale and promote a positive workplace attitude.

Addressing Lack of Recognition and Poor Job Satisfaction Among TMG Employees in Lemery

To further enhance recognition and job satisfaction among TMG employees, it is recommended that the municipality of Lemery continue to develop and refine its recognition and support programs. Expanding overtime compensation policies to ensure transparency and fairness can solidify the municipality's commitment to equitable treatment. Further investment in specialized training programs for emergency management can continuously improve employee readiness and confidence. Establishing a formal system for regular acknowledgment of extra responsibilities, including rewards or incentives, would provide tangible appreciation for employees' contributions. Additional health and safety protocols, such as the provision of protective gear and climate-controlled workstations, can further mitigate the risks associated with adverse working conditions. Implementing debriefing sessions and counseling services would provide emotional support for employees regularly dealing with difficult situations. Ensuring consistent access to necessary resources would empower TMG employees to respond efficiently to challenges without needing to improvise. Finally, maintaining and expanding community engagement initiatives will reinforce TMG employees' sense of belonging and pride in their role, while also encouraging public appreciation for their efforts in maintaining traffic safety and order.

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